

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

APRIL 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

ECHOES

of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue IV (April 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

GLENN PAULO K. LABASAN

Ifugao State University
Ifugao, Cordillera Administrative Region, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19429180

My First Hero

I remember how strong you've always been,
Holding us close through thick and thin.
I remember the battles you fought each day,
Keeping our family from drifting away.

I remember the tears you tried to hide,
Wiping them gently, turning aside.
I remember your care when we were small,
You gave your best, you gave your all.

You are the shoulder where others lean,
A kinder soul I've never seen.
You lend your hand to those in need,
With love and grace in every deed.

You've known betrayal, you've felt the pain,
From those who left like pouring rain.
Yet still you stayed, so calm, so true,
Because your children mattered to you.

You taught me fairness, respect, and care,
To lead with courage, to always be fair.
To dream, to strive, to kneel and pray,
And face each trial that comes my way.

Your heart is pure, your soul so bright,
A guiding star, a constant light.
Though years may pass and time may show,
Your love is all we'll ever know.

Your hair may fade to silver gray,
Your strength may slowly drift away,
But still you shine in all you do
A morning light, forever new.